

1 **Supplemental Materials for “Modeling Long-Term Flow Regimes in**
2 **Ungauged Basins: An Evaluation of Machine Learning Performance and**
3 **Uncertainty”**

4 **Supplement 1: Station Screening and Gauging-Station Database**

5 immediate

6 **INTRODUCTION**

7 This supplemental material presents the criteria used for selecting streamflow gauging stations
8 employed in analyses and validation within this manuscript. It refers to an effort of the project
9 “Cooperation in Technologies for Hydrological Analyses at National Scale”, established through
10 a Decentralized Execution Agreement (TED) between the Hydraulic Research Institute of the
11 Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (IPH/UFRGS) and the Brazilian National Water and
12 Sanitation Agency (ANA). The original report was written in Portuguese and is available through
13 the institutional repository of the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul ([Gama et al. 2021](#)).

14 **SELECTION AND ANALYSIS OF STREAMFLOW OBSERVATIONS FROM**
15 **GAUGING STATIONS FOR VALIDATION**

16 To construct the streamflow gauging database used in the analyses of this project, previous
17 applications, existing datasets (e.g., CAMELS-BR; [Chagas et al. 2020](#)), and the need for a new
18 station selection procedure were considered.

19 Streamflow observations from the ANA database and from other agencies/institutions, including
20 institutions outside Brazil, were used. ANA stations were selected using filters excluding stations
21 with drainage areas smaller than 10,000 km² and/or stations with less than five years of avail-
22 able data. In addition, stations potentially affected by reservoirs were discarded through manual
23 inspection of hydrographs. Approximately 410 stations were ultimately retained.

24 The CAMELS-BR database (Catchment Attributes and Meteorology for Large-sample Studies
25 – Brazil; Chagas et al. 2020) provides a selection of 817 stations. These stations resulted from a
26 sequence of filters applied to the original ANA database, removing: stations with less than one
27 year of available data during 1990–2009; stations with measurements of $0 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ representing
28 missing values; stations with flows on the order of 1000 mm day^{-1} ; stations with annual streamflow
29 exceeding observed precipitation; and stations presenting repeated identical values for several
30 consecutive days. This inspection was also manually performed.

31 For the present application, it was decided that stations should not be filtered based on drainage
32 area and that excluding the entire streamflow series due to isolated errors would be impractical, as
33 performed in CAMELS-BR. Therefore, a new database was developed.

34 To this end, all streamflow gauging stations available in the ANA database (15,536 stations)
35 were downloaded and the following filtering sequence was applied:

- 36 1. Exclusion of stations with less than two years of available data between 01/01/1979 and
37 12/31/2014;
- 38 2. Measurements identified as $0 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ representing missing values were converted to missing
39 data. Identification was automated considering that, at stations with Q90 greater than
40 zero, zero-flow values represent missing values; and that, at stations with Q90 equal to
41 zero, measurements of $0 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ occurring near missing values or when streamflow on the
42 previous day exceeded $50 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ also represent missing values;
- 43 3. Constant streamflow values over long periods were converted to missing data. The number
44 of repetitions of each measurement value along the available series was analyzed. If the
45 most repeated value occurred more than 1.5 times the repetition count of 99% of all other
46 values, this value was considered invalid whenever occurring on consecutive days;
- 47 4. Measurements greater than 1000 mm day^{-1} and negative streamflow values were converted
48 to missing data;
- 49 5. Stations located on river reaches with $\text{DOR} > 5$, according to the procedure described in
50 Section S3, were considered influenced by reservoirs and excluded from the database.

51 At the end of this process, approximately 2,000 streamflow gauging stations remained. However,
52 after this automatic filtering sequence, some stations still exhibited inconsistent measurements, such
53 as noise in the time series, unrealistic extreme values, abrupt changes in temporal behavior, and
54 reservoir operation effects. These stations were removed following manual inspection. Figure S1.1
55 presents examples of hydrographs considered inconsistent; the corresponding gauging stations were
56 therefore removed from the project database. The resulting dataset after the manual inspection
57 contains 1,069 streamflow gauging stations.

58 **HYDROREFERENCING OF STREAMFLOW GAUGING STATIONS AND** 59 **SUB-BASIN DATABASE**

60 To process streamflow data from gauging stations and develop the regionalized streamflow
61 database and associated uncertainties compatible with the BHO5K, it is necessary to establish a
62 relationship between station locations and the hydrographic database.

63 This process, referred to here as hydroreferencing, can be performed through distance-based
64 operations between gauging stations and BHO river reaches. Stations are geometrically represented
65 as points, whereas river reaches are represented as lines. In principle, the BHO reach closest to the
66 gauging station location provides the best hydroreferencing solution. Therefore, a nearest-neighbor
67 search between stations and reaches should be sufficient.

68 However, database limitations may require additional criteria. Examples include uncertainties
69 in the recorded coordinates of the streamflow gauging station relative to the actual measurement
70 location, as well as limitations related to the resolution of the BHO5K reach representation and its
71 compatibility with the actual course of the drainage network. In general, difficulties occur when
72 station coordinate errors place stations near confluences or between two rivers.

73 Beyond proximity criteria, comparing drainage area values between stations and BHO reaches
74 allows evaluation of hydroreferencing quality, although this criterion alone is insufficient. Due
75 to the resolution of the hydrographic network, differences may exist between the drainage area
76 recorded for the streamflow gauging station and the drainage area represented in the BHO, even
77 when the point is associated with the nearest reach and is in the best possible location. This effect

78 may occur because the station drainage area was not calculated using the same procedure as the
79 hydrographic network. The position of the station relative to the downstream and upstream nodes
80 of the nearest reach may also lead to differences.

81 After applying nearest-neighbor search, for example by snapping, Figure S1.2 illustrates the
82 hydroreferenced stations. Considering the initial database of 2,697 stations, 2,370 stations presented
83 relative error smaller than 30%, and 2,274 stations presented relative error smaller than 15%,
84 within a search radius of approximately 1.5 km. Additionally, 47 stations exhibited errors above
85 this threshold but were located at the best possible position. Figures S1.3 and S1.4 illustrate the
86 selection of stations with errors between 15 and 30%, and above 30%, respectively.

87 Alternative methodologies may consider additional features, such as polygons of hydrological
88 contribution areas, informative attributes such as river names, upstream/downstream tests, among
89 others. On the other hand, stations with considerable errors in the nearest-neighbor search indicate
90 some incompatibility between station coordinates and the BHO network.

91 Figure S1.5 shows that differences between the drainage areas of streamflow gauging stations and
92 hydroreferenced reaches tend to decrease with relative position from the headwaters, as measured
93 by the Strahler number. For reaches with Strahler number equal to 1, lower compatibility is evident,
94 at least according to the drainage-area metric. Figure S1.6 presents the same relationship after
95 removing all reaches with relative drainage-area differences greater than 30%. Finally, Figure S1.7
96 presents a filter that removes reaches showing inconsistency when comparing station drainage area
97 against the drainage areas of the downstream and upstream nodes of the selected network reach.

98 After screening the hydroreferenced streamflow gauging stations, a polygon database represent-
99 ing the upstream drainage area of each station was generated by traversing the upstream contribution
100 areas of each location, including the location itself, in the BHO. The database was stored both as in-
101 dividual GeoPackage files per streamflow gauging station and as a single combined file. Figure S1.8
102 illustrates the database after applying filters to improve visualization of overlapping basins.

103 This polygon database of upstream basins for each streamflow gauging station allows the analysis
104 of internal watershed variables when necessary for developing alternative methods or benchmarks.

105 Figure S1.9 presents the data structure and attribute table of the sub-basin database associated with
106 hydroreferenced streamflow gauging stations.

107 **DEGREE OF REGULATION (DOR)**

108 To evaluate the performance of different methodologies for estimating reference streamflows, it
109 is necessary to identify and discard streamflow gauging stations strongly affected by flow regulation,
110 since streamflow values calculated from observed series at these locations do not represent natural
111 streamflow.

112 The Brazilian hydrographic network and national water-body database are marked by a large
113 number of reservoirs used for different purposes, such as hydropower generation, water supply, and
114 irrigation. In this context, there are locations where the reservoir regulation effect, that is, alteration
115 of the natural hydrological regime, is more pronounced.

116 In general, it is not possible to know the degree of alteration of the hydrological regime caused
117 by a reservoir without knowing its operating rule. This rule is unknown for many reservoirs and
118 does not even exist in some cases, such as reservoirs of the National Interconnected System (SIN),
119 which operate according to a national-scale optimization logic.

120 However, reservoir impacts on hydrological regimes can be approximately estimated using a
121 simplified metric called Degree of Regulation (DOR), proposed by [Lehner et al. 2011](#).

122 DOR is defined as the ratio between the sum of useful storage volumes of reservoirs upstream
123 of a river reach and the mean annual streamflow, expressed as volume, passing through that reach.
124 It is therefore an index that quantifies the effect of reservoirs relative to the natural river regime.
125 DOR may also be interpreted as a measure of residence time expressed as a percentage of one year.
126 The DOR calculation at a location indexed by j is given by Equation S1.

$$127 \quad DOR_j = \frac{100}{D_j} \sum_{i=1}^{n_j} S_{ij} \quad (S1)$$

128 where j is the index of the location of interest; D_j is the mean streamflow, expressed as volume,
129 at location j ; S_{ij} is the volume of reservoir i upstream of the location of interest; and n_j is the total

130 number of reservoirs upstream of the location of interest.

131 According to Equation S1, DOR values may range from 0 to greater than 100. A value of 0
132 means that the hydrological regime in the reach is not affected by upstream regulation. A value
133 equal to 50 in a river reach means that the total useful storage volume of all upstream reservoirs is
134 able to sustain the mean streamflow of the river in that reach for 50% of a year.

135 To estimate DOR for each BHO river reach, the database named *Massas d'água* (Fuckner 2020),
136 which is compatible with BHO5K2017 and contains identifiers for dam locations, was used. First,
137 the volume reported in ANA's *Massas d'água* database was considered for water bodies identified
138 as regularization or ONS regularization. Subsequently, storage values were inserted and/or replaced
139 at 115 locations for which useful storage data were available from the National Electric System
140 Operator – National Interconnected System. In general, for reservoirs where no information on
141 useful storage is available, the reported volume is assumed to be useful storage for the purpose of
142 applying the methodology.

143 For each river reach, the total upstream useful storage volume was calculated and compared with
144 the mean streamflow from ANA's water availability database using Equation S1, thereby obtaining
145 the DOR value.

146 The map in Figure S1.10 highlights rivers with DOR greater than 0, that is, reaches affected
147 in some way by the presence of upstream reservoirs. Intensely affected reaches can be observed
148 downstream of the Serra da Mesa dam on the Tocantins River, and on the Paraíba do Sul, Parnaíba,
149 Grande, and São Francisco rivers, among others.

150 The hydroreferencing information for streamflow gauging stations and the DOR values of
151 BHO5K2017 reaches were compared, allowing the DOR metric to be estimated for each streamflow
152 gauging station. Thus, streamflow gauging stations with different degrees of regulation influence
153 can be identified, as shown in Figures S1.11, S1.12, and S1.13.

154 **HYDROLOGICAL NEIGHBORHOOD**

155 Post-processing methods and alternative methods for estimating streamflow at ungauged loca-
156 tions, used as benchmarks, are not yet fully defined, but will likely be based on some measure of

157 neighborhood between streamflow gauging stations, between a gauging station and an ungauged
158 reach, and between ungauged reaches.

159 In many cases, simple Euclidean distance between streamflow gauging stations, or Euclidean
160 distance between watershed centroids, is not adequate for evaluating proximity between two stream-
161 flow gauging stations. A more appropriate alternative metric for evaluating hydrological proximity
162 between two points located on the drainage network is the Jaccard index, which measures the degree
163 of nesting between two watersheds.

164 The Jaccard index for two watersheds is a similarity measure, with values between 0 and 1,
165 that measures the ratio between the area defined by the intersection of the two basins and the area
166 defined by their union, according to Equation S2. In nested basins, the Jaccard index has a value
167 corresponding to the area of the smaller basin divided by the area of the larger basin; therefore, its
168 maximum value is 1. In non-nested basins, the index value is zero.

$$169 \quad J(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} \quad (S2)$$

170 Figure S1.14 illustrates selected cases with their corresponding Jaccard index values. It can be
171 observed that, in the case with $J = 0.77$, similarity between basins is higher than in the case with
172 $J = 0.16$.

173 In non-nested basins, where the Jaccard index is zero, proximity between watersheds may be
174 estimated by the Euclidean distance between basin centroids, as illustrated in Figure S1.15. This
175 metric was also calculated for all pairs of basins associated with the streamflow gauging stations in
176 the selected database.

177 Thus, it was possible to produce tables relating neighborhood measures, such as the Jaccard
178 index and the distance between centroids. Figure S1.16 illustrates examples of these tables.

179 Figure S1.17 presents an example basin with streamflow gauging stations, associated sub-basins,
180 and minibasin centroids. This representation shows that there are different possibilities for support
181 stations to be used in a regionalization procedure in this neighborhood.

182 Figure S1.18 illustrates the Euclidean distance between station locations, a simple proximity

183 measure. In this example, the station in the red basin is closer to the station at the outlet of the blue
184 basin, whereas the station in the green basin is farther away.

185 Figure S1.19 presents a representation of the Jaccard index, showing the percentage of overlap-
186 ping area between nested basins. In this case, the red basin presents a low index, whereas the green
187 basin presents a higher index.

188 Finally, Figure S1.20 shows the distance between sub-basin centroids, where the central sub-
189 basin has the shortest distance. Figure S1.21 also illustrates the case of neighboring non-nested
190 basins, where the Jaccard index between them is zero, but distance measures may still be used.

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Fig. S1.1. Examples of streamflow gauging stations with inconsistent data series that were removed from the project database through manual inspection.

Fig. S1.2. Map of hydroreferenced streamflow gauging stations.

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Fig. S1.5. Relationship between Strahler number and relative error between drainage areas (BHO reach versus associated streamflow gauging station) on a logarithmic scale.

Fig. S1.6. Relationship between Strahler number and relative error between drainage areas (BHO reach versus associated streamflow gauging station) for a 30% tolerance.

Fig. S1.7. Relationship between Strahler number and relative error between drainage areas (BHO reach versus associated streamflow gauging station) for a 30% tolerance, with verification of station drainage area relative to the upstream and downstream drainage areas of the selected reach.

Fig. S1.8. Illustration of the sub-basin database for hydroreferenced streamflow gauging stations.

base_hidroref_snap.gpkg

Geopackage para cada bacía

- Nome
- bačia_10064000.gpkg
- bačia_10100000.gpkg
- bačia_10200000.gpkg
- bačia_10300000.gpkg
- bačia_10500000.gpkg
- bačia_10800000.gpkg
- bačia_10900000.gpkg
- bačia_10910000.gpkg
- bačia_11400000.gpkg
- bačia_11450000.gpkg
- bačia_11500000.gpkg
- bačia_12150000.gpkg
- bačia_12180000.gpkg
- bačia_12200000.gpkg
- bačia_12230000.gpkg
- bačia_12240000.gpkg
- bačia_12360000.gpkg
- bačia_12370000.gpkg
- bačia_12390000.gpkg
- bačia_12400000.gpkg
- bačia_12420000.gpkg
- bačia_12500000.gpkg
- bačia_12510000.gpkg
- bačia_12520000.gpkg
- bačia_12530000.gpkg
- bačia_12540000.gpkg
- bačia_12550000.gpkg

Geopackage completo

base_subbacias.gpkg

fid	posto	cotrecho	nuareamont
1	10064000	77141	114294.0198427...
2	10100000	77141	877328.5172472...
3	10200000	461216	16421.67099642...
4	10300000	102779	25254.5453189787
5	10500000	102779	61300.34620768...
6	10800000	51928	18848.33642515...
7	10900000	51928	18848.33642515...
8	10910000	224189	36642.51081718...
9	11400000	77141	996421.2143706...
10	11450000	369789	106916.8343505...
11	11500000	77141	1136357.465184...
12	12150000	68079	17527.74770367...
13	12180000	344828	12855.9780171864
14	12200000	68079	35571.91373803...
15	12230000	138273	10909.74625106...
16	12240000	68079	64521.41411253...
17	12360000	15125	7725.600046410...
18	12370000	15125	16128.75815215...
19	12390000	179912	22212.4135337882
20	12400000	85496	1118.632447456...
21	12420000	85496	5163.141690774...
22	12500000	428344	37865.48060041...
23	12510000	20161	3117.34610952245
24	12520000	428344	55929.43826097...

Fig. S1.9. Representation of the database and attribute table of sub-basins associated with hydroreferenced streamflow gauging stations.

Fig. S1.10. Estimated Degree of Regulation (DOR) in BHO5K2017, showing only reaches with DOR > 0.1.

Fig. S1.11. Maps of Degree of Regulation at hydroreferenced streamflow gauging station locations: no significant effect (left), $0 < DOR < 2$ (center), and $DOR < 5$ (right).

Fig. S1.12. Maps of Degree of Regulation at hydroreferenced streamflow gauging station locations: *DOR* > 5 (left), *DOR* up to 10 (center), and *DOR* > 20 (right).

Fig. S1.13. Maps of Degree of Regulation at hydroreferenced streamflow gauging station locations, with $DOR > 0$.

Fig. S1.14. Example of the relationship between areas of nested basins, represented by the Jaccard index.

Fig. S1.15. Example of distance between basin centroids.

Tabela do índice de Jaccard

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1		cotrecho	totrecho	jaccard	jusante	
2	0	993548	25130	0.130275	2	
3	1	993548	99306	0.114705	2	
4	2	993548	40650	0.100579	2	
5	3	993548	7241	0.064338	2	
6	4	993548	86886	0.05185	2	
7	5	993548	102619	0.026264	2	
8	6	993548	28970	0.024461	2	
9	7	25130	99306	0.88048	2	
10	8	25130	40650	0.772053	2	
11	9	25130	7241	0.49386	2	
12	10	25130	86886	0.398002	2	
13	11	25130	102619	0.201601	2	
14	12	25130	28970	0.187766	2	
15	13	48788	106442	0.267889	2	
16	14	48788	99306	0.016481	2	
17	15	48788	40650	0.014451	2	
18	16	48788	7241	0.009244	2	
19	17	48788	86886	0.00745	2	
20	18	48788	102619	0.003774	2	
21	19	48788	28970	0.003515	2	
22	20	988237	106442	0.41198	2	
23	21	988237	99306	0.025345	2	

20090 pares
subbacias de cotrechos hidrorreferenciados

Tabela das distâncias de centróides

	A	B	C	D	E
1		posto 1	posto 2	distance deg	
2	0	10100000	11400000	0.472440207	
3	1	10200000	10300000	0.975666399	
4	2	10200000	10500000	0.874412041	
5	3	10200000	13150000	0.821472069	
6	4	10300000	10500000	0.455450233	
7	5	10300000	10800000	0.904174618	
8	6	10300000	10900000	0.904174618	
9	7	10300000	13150000	0.934942874	
10	8	10300000	14100000	0.749653342	
11	9	10500000	13150000	0.500925917	
12	10	10500000	14100000	0.906415687	
13	11	10800000	10900000	0	
14	12	10800000	10910000	0.306690906	
15	13	10800000	14100000	0.303826876	
16	14	10900000	10910000	0.306690906	
17	15	10900000	14100000	0.303826876	
18	16	10910000	14100000	0.582007736	
19	17	11400000	11500000	0.646955106	
20	18	12150000	12180000	0.884005202	
21	19	12150000	12200000	0.532788499	
22	20	12180000	12200000	0.399180062	
23	21	12180000	12240000	0.620028216	

39080 pares
postos fluviométricos (raio de 100 km)

Fig. S1.16. Example tables containing the Jaccard index, calculated for BHO reaches, and centroid distances, calculated up to 100 km for streamflow gauging stations.

Fig. S1.17. Example of a basin with streamflow gauging stations (left), sub-basins (center), and centroids (right).

Fig. S1.18. Illustrative example of Euclidean distances between streamflow gauging stations.

Fig. S1.19. Illustrative example of the Jaccard index.

Distância de Centróides de Sub bacias

$D_c = 97$ km

$D_c = 33$ km

$D_c = 68$ km

Fig. S1.20. Illustrative example of distance between sub-basin centroids.

Fig. S1.21. Illustrative example of possible neighboring basins for the red basin, considering non-nested neighboring basins.